

Conference Abstract

Interdisciplinary biotechnological approach for analysis and modulation of the biological potential of the medicinal plant *Nepeta nuda*

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Abstract

This study on medicinal plants focuses primarily on non-enzymatic defense mechanisms, which have applications in plant science, traditional and modern medicine, the food industry, pharmacology, and cosmetics (Zhiponova et al. 2022). A key characteristic of biologically active compounds is their dependence on developmental and environmental factors. *Nepeta nuda* (catnip; Lamiaceae) is a medicinal plant rich in secondary metabolites and known for its adaptability, prompting us to adopt a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach to better understand this relatively understudied species.

First, the taxonomic position of *N. nuda* was determined using DNA barcoding. Phytochemical analysis of *N. nuda* extracts identified various compounds, including phenolic acids and their derivatives, flavonoids, iridoids, and primary metabolites (Petrova et al. 2022, Petrova et al. 2024, Zaharieva et al. 2023). The aqueous extracts exhibited the strongest antitumor effect against colon cancer cells, primarily through a proapoptotic mechanism (Gospodinova et al. 2024).

Comparative analyses between wild-grown (naturally occurring or *ex vitro* adapted) and *in vitro*-cultivated plants revealed that metabolic changes were associated with biological activities such as antioxidant, anti-herpesvirus, and anti-inflammatory effects (Petrova et al. 2022, Petrova et al. 2023, Petrova et al. 2024, Zaharieva et al. 2023). Interestingly, the

antimicrobial potential remained largely consistent across different growth conditions (Petrova et al. 2022, Petrova et al. 2024). The highest bioactive compound content was found in flowers and leaves, while in vitro-grown plants showed a marked reduction (Petrova et al. 2022, Zaharieva et al. 2023).

Phytochemical production was shown to be regulated by phytohormones, with light and temperature identified as key environmental signals influencing gene expression and plant physiology (Zhiponova et al. 2024, Zhiponova et al. 2025). These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the regulatory mechanisms underlying metabolic biosynthesis in plant species rich in biologically active compounds (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Summary of *Nepeta nuda* project.

Keywords

biological activities, light, metabolites, *Nepeta nuda*, physiology, temperature

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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